

The SENSEI Generic *In Situ* Interface’s Use of Ascent as an Endpoint

Burlen Loring¹, Nicole J. Marsaglia², and E. Wes Bethel¹[0000–0003–0790–7716]

¹ Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Berkeley CA, 94720, USA
[ewbethel,boring]@lbl.gov

² University of Oregon, Eugene OR, 97403, USA
marsagli@uoregon.edu

Abstract. The SENSEI generic *in situ* interface makes it possible for a simulation code to be instrumented once, then to connect to any number of different endpoints in an *in situ* or *in transit* processing configuration. This paper describes engineering enhancements that enable SENSEI-instrumented data producers to take advantage of Ascent-based endpoints in either *in situ* or *in transit* processing configurations, along with examples that demonstrate this new capability.

Keywords: SENSEI *in situ* interface · Ascent endpoint · code coupling

1 Introduction

In the realm of *in situ* processing, a simulation is instrumented with code to facilitate connecting to third-party tools that perform processing, such as analysis or visualization. Given the large and growing number of third-party tools, two related problems arise. The first is the fact that there is likely a different API for each of these tools. The second is that there is likely a different data model representation used by each of these tools.

The SENSEI generic *in situ* interface focuses on solving both problems. Its key objective is to make it possible for a SENSEI-instrumented data producer, such as a numerical simulation, to make use of any of a number of different external tools and applications for *in situ* processing, and to do so without requiring any instrumentation code changes when going from one tool to another.

Over the course of the SENSEI project [11], work has included performance analysis at extreme levels of concurrency [1] with *in situ* processing using SENSEI-enabled connections to tools like VisIt/Libsim [13] and ParaView/Catalyst [3]. The flexible nature of the SENSEI interface has accommodated growth in the number and diversity of endpoints, such as generic user-written parallel-capable Python code [9], as well as leveraging a diversity of *in transit* transport options [5] that enable support of scalable M-to-N processing scenarios [8].

Recent work in the SENSEI project has resulted in the ability to leverage the specialized collection of endpoints from the Ascent project [7]. This paper describes the engineering enhancements needed in SENSEI to support *in situ* and *in transit* connections between SENSEI-instrumented data producers and Ascent endpoints, along with some examples of this new capability.

2 Background

2.1 The SENSEI Generic *In Situ* Interface

The SENSEI interface is comprised of three components, which are shown in Figure 1. The *data adaptor* performs a mapping from the simulation data model to the VTK data model. The *analysis adaptor* performs a mapping from the VTK data model to that used by the *in situ* analysis methods. The bridge links together the data adaptor and the analysis adaptor, and provides the API that a simulation uses to trigger the invocation of the *in situ* methods. In this design and implementation, the VTK data model is the bridge data model between producer and consumer. Through SENSEI’s XML-based runtime configuration file, SENSEI’s *configurable analysis adaptor* (not shown) is responsible for selecting the appropriate `AnalysisAdaptor`, which in turn establishes the connection to a specific endpoint.

Fig. 1. The SENSEI bridge includes a `DataAdaptor`, seen by the simulation code or data producer, an `AnalysisAdaptor`, seen by the analysis code or data consumer, a bridge data model, and machinery to link the two adaptors. This image adapted from Ayachit et al., 2016 [2].

The process of adding a new endpoint to run in this environment consists of creating an `AnalysisAdaptor` that maps from the SENSEI bridge data model, namely the VTK data model, into the data model used by the endpoint method, as well as providing API hooks for three methods: `initialize`, `execute`, and `finalize`. This basic design pattern is the basis for a diverse collection of parallel-capable endpoints: for user-written Python code [9]; for data transports based on HDF5 [5], ADIOS [8], and libIS [12]; and for VisIt/Libsim and ParaView/Catalyst [1], among others. The focus of the present work is to extend this basic design principle to make use of the Ascent *in situ* library as a SENSEI endpoint.

2.2 Ascent

Ascent [7] is an easy-to-use “flyweight” *in situ* visualization and analysis library for HPC simulations. It uses Conduit’s Mesh Blueprint [6] as the “bridge” data model between data producer and consumer. Ascent leverages VTK-m [10] for

```

<sensei>
  <analysis type="ascent" actions="random_2d_64_ascent.json" enabled="1" >
    <mesh name="mesh">
      <cell_arrays> data </cell_arrays>
    </mesh>
  </analysis>
</sensei>

```

Listing 1: ConfigurableAnalysis XML for the AscentAnalysisAdaptor.

access to a diverse set of visualization methods that run in parallel using device-specific acceleration techniques.

In the context of this work, our implementation makes use of Ascent's API for the purposes of initialization, specification of a specific Ascent processing pipeline, handing mesh data to Ascent for processing, and graceful shutdown at the conclusion of a run.

3 Design and Implementation

3.1 SENSEI Interface Core Design Pattern

SENSEI presents *in situ* methods to simulations through its `AnalysisAdaptor` API. On the receiver, or consumer side, analysis codes then access simulation data structures through SENSEI's `DataAdaptor` API. A *bridge* code integrates SENSEI into the simulation, manages the adaptors and periodically invokes the analysis. Via an XML configuration file, SENSEI enables the simulation to select between different analysis back ends at run time.

For our Ascent endpoint, we make use of SENSEI's `AnalysisAdaptor` API, which consists of two virtual methods, `Execute` and `Finalize`, for which we must provide implementations. Integration into SENSEI's `ConfigurableAnalysis`, which selects the analysis back end at runtime via a user provided XML configuration file, requires implementation of a non-virtual `Initialize` method and a snippet of code to parse user provided XML tags from which run time configuration is received.

3.2 SENSEI Ascent Analysis Adaptor

Initialize method. When invoked by SENSEI's `ConfigurableAnalysis` mechanism, the `AscentAnalysisAdaptor Initialize` method is provided some parameters that are specified by the user in a SENSEI XML configuration file (c.f., Listing 1). The most important of these parameters is an Ascent JSON configuration file, which specifies the Ascent methods that will be invoked, their parameters, and so forth. During this `Initialize` method, the SENSEI code will invoke the appropriate Ascent methods to load the JSON configuration file, and test Ascent's return status for errors.

Fig. 2. Three images produced *in situ* by Ascent when coupled to a SENSEI-instrumented code and using the new SENSEI `AscentAnalysisAdaptor`.

Execute method. Over the course of the simulation run, when the simulation invokes the SENSEI `Execute`, the call chain then invokes the `Execute` method in the `AscentAnalysisAdaptor`. The primary activity in this function is to map from SENSEI’s bridge data model, the VTK data model, into the Conduit data model, to invoke Conduit’s methods to pass this data on to Ascent, and to invoke Ascent’s `Execute` method.

Finalize method. When the simulation has come to an end and invokes the SENSEI `Finalize` method, the call chain will invoke a `Finalize` method in the `AscentAnalysisAdaptor`. This method will in turn invoke an Ascent `close` method.

4 Results

As part of a tutorial at SC20 [4], we demonstrated the use of an Ascent endpoint coupled with a SENSEI-instrumented code. One instance is a direct *in situ* coupling, while another is an *in transit* coupling that uses ADIOS for data movement between producer and consumer.

In this particular problem, one of the SENSEI miniapplications, `oscillators`, is configured to run over a number of time steps as it models the movement of waves through space produced by multiple oscillator sources positioned on a grid. The visualization methods in Ascent leveraged for this demonstration include a psuedocolored slice along with a single contour level. The SENSEI configuration file for the *in situ* use of Ascent is shown in Listing 1, and three images from different points in time are shown in Fig. 2.

5 Conclusion

One of the impacts of this work is the ability for SENSEI-instrumented codes to leverage a nice body of work present in the Ascent project. These capabilities include the ability to perform distributed-memory, hardware-accelerated visualization and rendering, but without the use of full-scale applications, like VisIt or ParaView. This work is made possible by the underlying designs of both the SENSEI and Ascent software implementations.

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